

AMONOT: Synthetic Aging for Differential Morphing Attack Detection Systems

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Abstract. Facial morphing attacks have become a serious threat to identity verification systems, especially in security-critical environments such as Automated Border Control gates. These attacks exploit the vulnerabilities of face recognition systems by merging two distinct identities into a single image, allowing both individuals to bypass verification processes. Current Morphing Attack Detection (MAD) systems face significant challenges in accurately detecting such manipulations when test images present peculiar characteristics, not well represented in the training data. Even though the impact of these factors has been addressed to some extent in the literature, the effects of natural biometric variations like aging have not yet been widely investigated. This paper proposes a novel dataset, AMONOT, consisting of synthetic aged images to assess the robustness of MAD systems to aging. By generating realistic synthetic faces with a granular age progression, we enable a more comprehensive evaluation of MAD systems under conditions that mimic real-world scenarios. The proposed dataset and experimental protocol aim to enhance the detection accuracy of morphing attacks involving aged faces, offering a more robust benchmark for improving security in identity verification applications.

Keywords: Morphing Attack · Morphing Attack Detection · Synthetic Images · Aging Systems · Biometrics · Face Recognition.

1 Introduction

Facial morphing attacks [27] have emerged as a significant security threat, particularly in identity verification systems such as those used in Automated Border Control (ABC) gates. A morphing attack occurs when two different facial identities are combined into a single image, allowing both individuals to be successfully matched by Face Recognition Systems (FRSs) with the same morphed document. This is especially problematic because such attacks can evade detection by both human operators and automated systems, posing risks to critical security applications like passport verification and criminal identification [36,38].

In this scenario, Morphing Attack Detection (MAD) systems [32] are designed to identify these morphed images and are crucial in protecting identity verification processes from being compromised. However, existing MAD methods struggle to provide reliable results due to various factors such as lack of common validation protocols and limited access to public datasets [4]. In addition, age progression, a natural biometric variation, further complicates the MAD task, as morphing attacks that include an aging factor can exacerbate the difficulty of detecting subtle manipulations in facial images over time. Aging is a very important issue in document verification since electronic Machine Readable Travel Documents (eMRTD) are typically designed to last for around 10 years [13]. Therefore, during this time range, significant changes in a person’s facial appearance must be accepted as normal variations within the same person’s identity in verification and MAD systems.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes a novel dataset, called AMONOT³, that integrates the use of synthetic images and aging systems to evaluate the robustness of MAD systems. This enables the evaluation of how well these systems perform when dealing with aging-induced variations, thereby offering a more robust method for benchmarking their accuracy under real-world conditions. In addition, AMONOT, containing only synthetic images, reduces the issues related to the privacy of individuals and simplifies the release and the use of the dataset in the literature and future works. At the best of our knowledge, this dataset is the first of its category.

Experimental evaluation is carried out on three state-of-the-art Differential MAD systems and reveals the strong need to take into account the aging effects in the training and development of new MAD systems in order to increase their robustness in real-world operational scenarios.

2 Related Works

2.1 Face Aging

In computer vision, face aging is a task that involves developing algorithms and models that can predict and simulate the gradual changes in facial features over time. In this context, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [20] have been extensively used due to their ability to generate high-quality and realistic images. Antipov et al. [1] have been among the first to employ conditional GANs [29] for face aging, achieving significant improvements in the realism of generated images. However, these early models often struggle with identity preservation, leading to a noticeable alteration of the person’s identity across different ages. Other approaches like HRFAE [44], which introduce high-resolution face age editing, and IPCGAN [43], which incorporate an identity-preserving module and an age classifier, have addressed these issues to varying degrees.

However, maintaining identity consistency across different ages is still a challenge. Re-Aging GAN (RAGAN) [26] tries to address this issue by proposing

³ <https://miatbiolab.csr.unibo.it/amonot-synthetic-aged-dataset>

an age modulator that learns high-order interactions between the given identity and the target age, effectively recalibrating identity information according to the target age. This approach allows for continuous and natural-looking age transformations across a wide range of ages while minimizing artifacts and preserving the individual’s identity.

Latent diffusion models represent a newer direction for face aging. In particular, Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPM) [21] are able to generate images whose quality is comparable or even superior to GANs. For instance, [19] introduced a custom structure preservation module that allows the adjusting of the degree of structural preservation during translation, enabling more profound changes in facial morphology while maintaining relevant details. The method FADING proposed by Chen et al. [8] adapts Stable Diffusion [34] for the face aging task, using a two-stage process involving specialization and editing. The model is first fine-tuned by using text prompts to guide localized age editing. This method has shown superior performance in maintaining visual realism and attribute consistency compared to previous approaches. [2] maintains biometric fidelity through contrastive and biometric losses, ensuring high visual realism and identity preservation. This method demonstrates significant improvements over existing baselines in reducing false non-match rates.

2.2 Face Morphing

Face morphing is a powerful and increasingly accessible technique that allows for the gradual transformation of one image into another (see Fig. 1). This method has become a significant concern in the realm of identity verification and security, as it can be exploited to create human faces with dual identities [27,15]. Indeed, these morphed faces can then be used to bypass automated face verification systems, as well as circumvent human controls and scrutiny [32].

Furthermore, the development of novel generative AI techniques for face morphing [45,42] has heightened concerns, as it simplifies the process for potential attackers. The morphed images can also be improved through manual or automated retouching [11,6], eliminating both visible and undetectable traces (artifacts). This emphasizes the urgent need to create MAD systems that can effectively detect and prevent new morphing attacks.

Concluding, addressing this challenge is essential to maintain the integrity of identity verification processes, protect against identity fraud, and ensure the overall security and trust in digital systems and interactions.

2.3 Morphing Attack Detection (MAD) Systems

The existing literature primarily outlines two types of MAD methods: Single-image MAD (S-MAD) and Differential MAD (D-MAD) [32,37]. S-MAD systems use only a single input image to detect artifacts or traces left by the morphing process, which can be challenging since it relies solely on the information within a single image. Conversely, D-MAD systems receive two distinct images as input: a trusted live capture and an image under examination. D-MAD systems can

Fig. 1: Visual samples of morphed images included in AMONOT obtained using three different morphing algorithms. Subjects acting as an accomplice and a criminal are depicted in the left and right columns, respectively.

leverage not only the detection of morphing traces in the input images, but also the comparison of the input identities or the analysis of the differences between the two images. Recently, a new category of MAD methods based on video sequences has been introduced and referred to as Video-based MAD (V-MAD) [5]. This category is based on the availability of facial video usually acquired by face verification systems at, for instance, border controls.

In this paper, we focus on the D-MAD category, since we take into account the operational scenario in which the document photo is compared to a trusted live image acquired, for instance, at ABC in international airports.

The work most similar to ours in the literature is reported in [41]. In this study, the authors test the impact of aging on MAD systems (not clear if based on a single or a pair of images in input). The investigation is conducted only with real photos of subjects from the MORPH dataset [33], and for this reason, the dataset containing morphed images is not publicly released. Additionally, the aging range is limited to 2-5 years, which does not allow for a thorough and granular analysis across different ages. Also considering this work, in our view, we believe aging may have a particularly significant impact on D-MAD methods due to the changes that aging induces in facial appearance.

3 AMONOT Dataset

In this paper, we aim to introduce a dataset that reproduces as accurately as possible a real operational scenario. Specifically, in the morphing attack, the morphing procedure is applied to document images, *i.e.* the images stored in eMRTD. These facial images, in order to be included in official documents, must follow strict quality requirements defined by ISO and ICAO institutions [23,24]. These guidelines specify various criteria such as the size and position of the face,

lighting, background uniformity, and facial expression to ensure that the photos represent an ideal scenario for automated face recognition systems such as the ones found in ABC gates at international airports.

Therefore, in the creation of the AMONOT dataset we include only ISO/ICAO compliant images, to increase the level of realism and efficacy of the tested solutions. Then, we apply aging systems to the images sourced from ONOT [12], a synthetic dataset specifically created to fulfill the ISO/ICAO requirements.

Starting from the ONOT images, aged and morphed probe images are generated - hence the name Aged Morphed ONOT (AMONOT) of the proposed dataset.

In particular, the AMONOT dataset is composed as follows:

- Bona fide document images: 255 high-quality mugshot pictures, conforming to the ISO/ICAO guidelines for official photos used for identification purposes, available in the ONOT dataset.
- Morphed document images: 7560 morphed images required for the experiments are generated by selecting the morph pairing candidates with high comparison scores based on three Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) FRSs. Each subject, referred to as “criminal” is compared with other individuals of the same gender and ethnicity, who serve as potential “accomplices”. Given a criminal subject, the five most similar subjects are selected as accomplices to maximize the probability of fooling FRSs at the gate. Then, the ISO/ICAO-compliant images of each subject pair have been morphed using six different SOTA landmark-based morphing algorithms (in this paper referred to as C01 [31], C02 [14], C03 [32], C05 [17,18], C15 [40,22], C16 [3]) using a morphing factor of 0.5, which results in an equal blending of facial features between the criminal and accomplice.
- Gate images: overall 1275 probe gate images, simulating the trusted live capture acquired at an ABC gate, are used in the experiments. In particular, for each subject in the dataset, at least one less-controlled probe image is selected from the ONOT dataset. Then, the aging process described in Section 3.1 is applied to these probe images, thus producing different versions of the same live image simulating different subject ages.

Representative samples of the morphed images are provided in Figure 1.

3.1 Generation of Aged Live Images

For each subject of the ONOT dataset, one ISO/ICAO compliant image is selected as reference bona fide and the image with the highest identity similarity score relative to it is selected and assigned the role of the live image. The similarity between the images is determined by computing the cosine similarity of AdaFace [25] facial embeddings. To simulate the effects of aging, the selected live image is artificially aged using a facial aging model. Among the others, we select HRFAE [44]⁴ and FADING [8]⁵ as our candidate face aging models. The aging

⁴ <https://github.com/InterDigitalInc/HRFAE>

⁵ <https://github.com/MunchkinChen/FADING>

Fig. 2: Visual sample of two aged and rejuvenated subjects. Starting from the original image in the central column, both subjects are rejuvenated (left) and aged (right).

process involves incrementally adding 5, 10, 15, and 20 years to the subject’s known original age, creating a series of aged images.

Furthermore, we compare the identity similarity between the original and the artificially aged images to ensure that a face recognition system is able to identify them as belonging to the same subject. This check is important since a common problem of generative models is the difficulty of preserving subject identity while applying other types of facial property modifications. This approach allows for the evaluation of how aging affects the performance of MAD systems, particularly when the subject’s age at the time of document issuance may differ significantly from their appearance at the time of verification.

4 Experimental Evaluations

For the experimental evaluation, we use the aging systems in two different ways. For the evaluation of aging (Sect. 4.1) and aged identities (Sect. 4.2), we both age and rejuvenate all ISO/ICAO images in the ONOT dataset in 10-year increments, starting from the subjects’ original ages to cover the range from 18 to 79 years. For instance, starting from an image of a 56-year-old person, we generate variants with ages 26, 36, 46, 66, and 76. Examples of both aging and rejuvenation are reported in Figure 2. We believe in this manner we evaluate the aging systems in a more comprehensive way.

For the evaluation of MAD systems (Sect. 4.3), we follow the generation procedure described in Section 3.1, in order to replicate the real-world operational scenario in which an electronic document is valid for about 10 years.

Fig. 3: Visual sample of the same subject aged through both FADING [8] (top row) and HRFAE [44] (bottom row) methods.

4.1 Evaluation of Aging

Our first experiments focus on evaluating which face aging model between HRFAE or FADING produces the most accurate results. First, we conduct a qualitative analysis by observing the generated images in Figure 3, and note that FADING presents a generally higher quality and consistency of results than HRFAE, given the same subject and the same age. Moreover, it can be noted that the changes proposed by FADING are much more noticeable, while HRFAE makes very few adjustments to the original image. Then, for a quantitative evaluation, we utilize the DEX [35] age estimator to compute the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between the expected and predicted ages. In addition, we aim to identify whether either of the aging models encounters difficulties when generating images within specific age ranges, thus detecting any biases or performance issues that may arise. To do so, we group all aged images according to their expected age into 10-year intervals and calculate the MAE for each distinct subset.

As depicted in Figure 4, FADING consistently outperforms HRFAE across all bins, indicating that the former exhibits superior generation quality across all age ranges. In contrast, HRFAE encounters difficulties in generating realistic images for subjects in the 10-19 and 70-79 expected age groups. This limitation is likely due to the fact that the training dataset for HRFAE predominantly includes subjects aged 20 to 69 years [44], leading to generally poor performance when generating subjects whose target age sits outside these bounds. Furthermore, we compute the overall MAE for FADING, which is equal to 5.74, significantly lower than the 24.99 observed for HRFAE. FADING’s overall better qualitative and quantitative results can be explained by the fact that the model requires both the gender and initial age of the subject, guiding the generation process to yield more accurate and photorealistic pictures. On the other hand, HRFAE only requires the desired target age of the subject.

Fig. 4: MAE across different expected age ranges for both face aging models. The error of FADING is low and constant, revealing a superior quality.

4.2 Evaluation of Aged Identities

In this section, in order to assess the validity of the aged probe set generated, we conduct identity consistency checks to ensure that the aging process does not result in excessive transformation of the subjects’ identities. For this purpose, we use AdaFace [25] to extract facial embeddings for each image and calculate the mean cosine distance between the original and altered images.

Experimental results are reported in Figure 5. Overall, as expected, the cosine distance increases proportionally to the age difference between the two images, despite always remaining under the threshold of 0.723. This threshold is computed by running face verification tests against the FRGC [30] dataset. In particular, a subset of 35k genuine/impostor pairs is chosen, and for each pair of images the cosine distance of the two facial embeddings is computed; therefore, the returned value should be low when the pair is genuine. Then, we obtain the face verification threshold by finding the one that results in a False Acceptance Rate (FAR) of 0.1%, meaning that for every 1000 impostor pairs only one is mistakenly identified as genuine. The FADING approach confirms its superiority w.r.t. HRFAE, as clearly visible in the overall lower cosine distances observed across all age ranges. Moreover, Figure 5b shows that HRFAE struggles to preserve the original identity even within the same age range, as shown by the bars whose label corresponds to the bins in the x-axis.

Furthermore, to better view how identity is preserved across images of the same subject that are close in age, we compute the mean cosine distance between pairs of pictures that differ by 10 years in expected age. Results, plotted by grouping the data according to the initial and final age ranges, are shown in Figure 6. Results show how HRFAE tends to cluster subjects into three broad age categories: young, middle-aged, and elderly. In contrast, FADING does not appear to exhibit a similar clustering pattern. In both models, the younger age

(a) FADING

(b) HRFAE

Fig. 5: Plot of mean cosine distance between original and aged images. The distance is computed between the original age (x-axis) and the generated age indicated with the corresponding color.

ranges present higher cosine distances, possibly due to the significant physical changes that occur during adolescence. These can cause greater variation in facial features, whereas identity becomes more stable in adulthood, resulting in lower cosine distances in older age groups.

4.3 Evaluation of D-MAD Methods across Aging

In this evaluation, we aim to simulate a realistic scenario in which the document image (possibly morphed) is compared to a trusted live capture that represents the subject with the same, near of different age.

Then, for the experimental evaluation, we selected some publicly available D-MAD systems [39,7,10,16] that obtain good performance in sequestered datasets⁶. Considering the observation of the previous sections, we select FADING as our

⁶ <https://biolab.csr.unibo.it/fvcongoing>

Fig. 6: Plot of mean cosine distance between pairs of images that differ by 10 years in expected age. Initial and final age ranges are reported on the x-axis.

aging system. The experimental protocol includes 255 bona fide attempts and 7560 morphed attempts obtained by systematically varying the age difference between the live image and the reference image in each pair (see Sect. 3).

The evaluation process begins by comparing images with no age difference (referred to as “baseline”), where the subject depicted in the document and the live image are the same age, to establish a reference for system accuracy. The testing then progresses to age differences of 5, 10, 15, and 20 years, where the subject in the live image is progressively older than in the reference image. Although comparing images with age differences of 15 and 20 years may appear unrealistic, this approach is valuable for examining the broader effects of aging on D-MAD systems, which might be less detectable with smaller age gaps.

For the results, we use common error-based metrics tailored for the MAD task. Specifically, we calculate the Bona Fide Presentation Classification Error Rate (BPCER), which measures the ratio of genuine images mistakenly classified as morphed. Conversely, the Morphing Attack Classification Error Rate (MACER) represents the ratio of morphed images incorrectly identified as genuine. In the literature, BPCER is often analyzed alongside a predetermined MACER threshold. In our experiments, we investigate $\text{BPCER}_{0.1}$ ($\mathbf{B}_{0.1}$), $\text{BPCER}_{0.05}$ ($\mathbf{B}_{0.05}$), and $\text{BPCER}_{0.01}$ ($\mathbf{B}_{0.01}$), which denote the lowest BPCER achievable when MACER does not exceed 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively. The $\text{BPCER}_{0.01}$ metric is a particularly stringent benchmark and is commonly used as the standard operational point for facial verification systems in real-world applications. These values are also visualized through the Detection Error Tradeoff (DET) curve, which is useful for directly comparing different solutions.

To aid comparison, for each method we also report the percentage variation of each metric w.r.t. the baseline, computed as $\Delta M_y = \frac{M_y - M_0}{M_0}$, where M_0 represents the baseline for metric M . Similarly, M_y represents metric M computed on images aged by adding y years to their original age. As shown in Table 1, all metrics progressively worsen as the subject’s age increases, probably due to the fact that all selected D-MAD methods rely on deep learning-based face recog-

Table 1: Performance of several D-MAD methods when varying the age gap between the document and live images. The term “baseline” indicates that the person depicted in the document and probe images show the same age.

MAD	Aging	EER	B _{0.1}	B _{0.05}	B _{0.01}	ΔEER	ΔB _{0.1}	ΔB _{0.05}	ΔB _{0.01}
[39]	Baseline	.180	.290	.447	.726	-	-	-	-
	+5 yrs	.208	.432	.561	.843	+15.3%	+48.7%	+25.4%	+16.2%
	+10 yrs	.286	.569	.702	.906	+58.8%	+95.9%	+57.0%	+24.9%
	+15 yrs	.349	.663	.777	.910	+93.6%	+128%	+73.7%	+25.4%
	+20 yrs	.394	.749	.824	.926	+118%	+158%	+84.2%	+27.6%
[7]	Baseline	.137	.231	.392	.769	-	-	-	-
	+5 yrs	.139	.224	.475	.867	+1.09%	-3.41%	+21.0%	+12.8%
	+10 yrs	.184	.404	.588	.878	+34.1%	+74.6%	+50.0%	+14.3%
	+15 yrs	.213	.494	.690	.894	+54.7%	+114%	+76.0%	+16.3%
	+20 yrs	.245	.588	.733	.886	+78.0%	+154%	+87.0%	+15.3%
[10]	Baseline	.127	.173	.271	.592	-	-	-	-
	+5 yrs	.154	.216	.369	.647	+21.0%	+25.0%	+36.2%	+9.27%
	+10 yrs	.227	.361	.506	.702	+78.5%	+109%	+87.0%	+18.5%
	+15 yrs	.267	.486	.600	.769	+110%	+182%	+122%	+29.8%
	+20 yrs	.271	.604	.682	.792	+112%	+250%	+152%	+33.8%
[16]	Baseline	.122	.149	.228	.565	-	-	-	-
	+5 yrs	.177	.251	.408	.706	+45.2%	+68.5%	+79.3%	+25.0%
	+10 yrs	.259	.435	.541	.788	+113%	+192%	+138%	+39.6%
	+15 yrs	.330	.569	.675	.831	+171%	+282%	+197%	+47.2%
	+20 yrs	.357	.659	.737	.918	+193%	+342%	+224%	+62.5%

dition models such as ArcFace [9] or MagFace [28] to output the final decision. Indeed, as shown in Section 4.2, these models, despite their general cross-age robustness, exhibit degraded performance on face verification when increasing the age gap between the two pictures of the subject, potentially affecting the final decision. In particular, [7] presents the least performance degradation w.r.t. aging probably due to the combined use of identity and artifact-related features. On the contrary, alternative approaches to deep learning such as [16] appear less resistant when increasing the subject’s age. As a visual summarization, Figure 7 depicts the DET curves for each D-MAD system when increasing the age gap.

5 Discussion on Synthetic Data

We recognize that the use of diffusion and generative models, which are trained on extensive datasets obtained from the internet, raises critical ethical, legal, and privacy concerns. However, our goal with the AMONOT dataset is to explore alternative methods for generating aged facial data that could potentially minimize the dependence on real-world and identifiable individuals. We understand

Fig. 7: Performance of considered D-MAD methods (here referred to as DFR [39], Siamese [7], ACIdA [10] and Demorphing [17]) across different age gaps in the live acquisition images.

that this approach may not completely resolve the intricate issues surrounding ethics and privacy in face recognition and related tasks.

6 Conclusions and Future Works

In this paper, we introduced AMONOT, a novel synthetic dataset designed to evaluate the robustness of Differential Morphing Attack Detection (D-MAD) systems against the challenges posed by aging. Our experiments demonstrated that as the age difference between the document and live image increases, the

performance of D-MAD systems significantly declines. This degradation is consistent across different algorithms, emphasizing the need to account for age-related facial variations when developing more resilient MAD systems.

The results suggest that it is important to account for aging effects in the training and evaluation protocols of MAD systems, especially in operational scenarios like border control, where individuals' facial appearance may change significantly over time. The AMONOT dataset, with its realistic simulation of facial aging, provides a valuable resource for advancing research in this domain.

For future work, we aim to extend the AMONOT dataset by introducing variations in aging systems, facial expressions, lighting conditions, and other real-world factors that further complicate morphing attack detection.

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